

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 34:0 <i>A Psalm</i> of David when he feigned madness before Abimelech, who drove him away and he departed.</p>	<p>Psa. 34:1 לְדָוִד בְּשִׁנּוֹתָיו אֶת־</p>
<p>Psa. 34:1 I will bless the LORD at all times;</p>	<p>טַעַמּוֹ לִפְנֵי אֲבִימֶלֶךְ וַיִּגְרֶשְׁהוּ</p>
<p>His praise shall continually be in my mouth.</p>	<p>וַיֵּלֶךְ : 2 אֲבָרְכָה אֶת־יְהוָה</p>
<p>² My soul will make its boast in the LORD;</p>	<p>בְּכָל־עֵת הַמְּיַד תְּהַלְתּוּ בְּפִי : 3</p>
<p>The humble will hear it and rejoice.</p>	<p>בִּיהוָה תִּתְהַלֵּל נַפְשִׁי יִשְׁמְעוּ</p>
<p>³ O magnify the LORD with me,</p>	<p>עֲנָנִים וַיִּשְׁמְחוּ : 4 גִּדְלוּ לִיהוָה</p>
<p>And let us exalt His name together.</p>	<p>אֶתִּי וְנִרְוַמְמָה שְׁמוֹ יַחְדָּו : 5</p>
<p>Psa. 34:4 I sought the LORD, and He answered me,</p>	<p>דַּרְשֵׁתִי אֶת־יְהוָה וְעָנָנִי וּמְכַל־</p>
<p>And delivered me from all my fears.</p>	<p>מְגֹדְרוֹתַי הִצִּילָנִי : 6 הִבִּיטוּ</p>
<p>⁵ They looked to Him and were radiant, And their faces will never be ashamed.</p>	<p>אֵלָיו וְנִתְהַרוּ וּפְנֵיהֶם אֵל־</p>
<p>⁶ This poor man cried, and the LORD heard him</p>	<p>יַחְפְּרוּ : 7 זֶה עָנִי קָרָא וַיִּתְּנָה</p>
<p>And saved him out of all his troubles.</p>	<p>שָׁמַע וּמְכַל־צָרוֹתָיו הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי : 8</p>
<p>⁷ The angel of the LORD encamps around those who fear Him, And rescues them.</p>	<p>חָנְנָה מִלְּאֵף־יְהוָה סָבִיב</p>
<p>Psa. 34:8 O taste and see that the LORD is good;</p>	<p>לִירְאָיו וַיִּתְלַצֵּם : 9 טַעַמּוֹ וַרְאוּ</p>
<p>How blessed is the man who takes refuge in Him!</p>	<p>כִּי־טוֹב יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר־יִתְּנֶנּוּ</p>
<p>⁹ O fear the LORD, you His saints; For to those who fear Him there is no want.</p>	<p>יַחְסֶה־בּוֹ : 10 יִרְאוּ אֶת־יְהוָה</p>
<p>¹⁰ The young lions do lack and suffer hunger;</p>	<p>קִדְשָׁיו כִּי־אֵין מִחֶסֶד לִירְאָיו :</p>
<p>But they who seek the LORD shall not be in want of any good thing.</p>	<p>11 כְּפִירִים רָשׁוּ וְרָעְבוּ וְדָרְשׁוּ</p>
<p>¹¹ Come, you children, listen to me;</p>	<p>יְהוָה לֹא־יַחְסְרוּ כָּל־טוֹב : 12</p>
<p>I will teach you the fear of the LORD.</p>	<p>לְכוּ־בָנִים שְׁמַעוּ־לִי יִרְאַת</p>
<p>¹² Who is the man who desires life And loves length of days that he may see good?</p>	<p>יְהוָה אֲלִמְדַּכֶּם : 13 מִי־הָאִישׁ</p>
<p>¹³ Keep your tongue from evil</p>	<p></p>

14 And your lips from speaking ^bdeceit.
‫אֲדַרְכּוּ מֵרָע וְנַעֲשֶׂה טוֹב׃
Seek peace and ^bpursue it.

Psa. 34:15 The ^aeyes of the LORD are toward the righteous
And His ears are *open* to their cry.

16 The ^aface of the LORD is against evildoers,

To ^ccut off the memory of them from the earth.

17 *The righteous* ^acry, and the LORD hears
And delivers them out of all their troubles.

18 The LORD ^ais near to the ^bbrokenhearted

And saves those who are ^ccrushed in spirit.

Psa. 34:19 ^aMany are the ^bafflictions of the righteous,

But the LORD ^cdelivers him out of them all.

20 He keeps all his bones,
^aNot one of them is broken.

21 ^aEvil shall slay the wicked,
And those who hate the righteous will be ^ccondemned.

22 The LORD ^aredeems the soul of His servants,

And none of those who ^ctake refuge in Him will be ^ccondemned.

הִתְחַפֵּץ תַּיִם אֲהַב יָמִים לְרְאוֹת
טוֹב׃ 14 נִצַּר לְשׁוֹנֵן מֵרָע

וְשִׁפְתָיו מִדַּבֵּר מִרְמָה׃ 15 סוֹר
מֵרָע וַעֲשֵׂה טוֹב בִּבְקֶשׁ שָׁלוֹם

וְרִדְפָהוּ׃ 16 עֵינֵי יְהוָה אֶל־
צְדִיקִים וְאֲזִנוֹ אֶל־שׁוֹעֲתָם׃ 17

פְּנֵי יְהוָה בְּעֵשִׂי רַע לְהַכְרִית
מֵאֶרֶץ זָכָרָם׃ 18 צָעֲקוּ וַיִּהְיֶה

שָׁמַע וּמָכַל־צְרוֹתָם הַצִּילָם׃ 19
קָרֹב יְהוָה לְנִשְׁבְּרֵי־לֵב וְאֶת־

דַּכְּאֵי־רוּחַ יוֹשִׁיעַ׃ 20 רַבּוֹת
רָעוֹת צְדִיק וּמְכַלֵּם יַצִּילָנוּ

יְהוָה׃ 21 שִׁמְרֵ כָּל־עֲצָמוֹתָיו
אֲתַת מִתְּהַנֶּה לֹא נִשְׁבָּרָה׃ 22

תְּמוֹתֶת רָשָׁע רָעָה וְשִׁנְאֵי צְדִיק
יִאֲשָׁמוּ׃ 23 פּוֹדֶה יְהוָה נַפְשׁ

עַבְדָּיו וְלֹא יִאֲשָׁמוּ כָּל־הַחַסִּים
בּוֹ׃ --

References

<p>Psalm 34:0 ¹Or <i>changed his behavior</i> ²Possibly a title of King Achish of Gath, see 1 Sam 21:10-15</p> <p>Psalm 34:1 ^aEph 5:20; 1 Thess 5:18 ^bPs 71:6</p> <p>Psalm 34:2 ^aPs 44:8; Jer 9:24; 1 Cor 1:31 ^bPs 69:32</p> <p>Psalm 34:3 ^aPs 35:27; 69:30; Luke 1:46 ^bPs 18:46</p> <p>Psalm 34:4 ^a2 Chr 15:2; Ps 9:10; Matt 7:7 ^bPs 34:6, 17, 19</p> <p>Psalm 34:5 ^aPs 36:9; Is 60:5 ^bPs 25:3</p> <p>Psalm 34:6 ¹Or <i>afflicted</i> ^aPs 34:4</p> <p>Psalm 34:7 ^aPs 91:11; Dan 6:22</p> <p>Psalm 34:8 ^aPs 119:103; Heb 6:5; 1 Pet 2:3 ^bPs 2:12</p>	<p>Psalm 34:9 ^aPs 31:23 ^bPs 23:1</p> <p>Psalm 34:10 ^aPs 84:11</p> <p>Psalm 34:11 ^aPs 66:16 ^bPs 32:8 ^cPs 111:10</p> <p>Psalm 34:12 ^aPs 34:12-16; 1 Pet 3:10-12 ^bEccl 3:13</p> <p>Psalm 34:13 ^aPs 141:3; Prov 13:3; James 1:26 ^b1 Pet 2:22</p> <p>Psalm 34:14 ^aPs 37:27; Is 1:16, 17 ^bRom 14:19; Heb 12:14</p> <p>Psalm 34:15 ^aJob 36:7; Ps 33:18</p> <p>Psalm 34:16 ^aLev 17:10; Jer 44:11; Amos 9:4 ^bJob 18:17; Ps 9:6; 109:15; Prov 10:7</p> <p>Psalm 34:17 ^aPs 34:6; 145:19</p>
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Psalm 34:18

¹Or *contrite*

^aPs 145:18

^bPs 147:3; Is 61:1

^cPs 51:17; Is 57:15

Psalm 34:19

^aProv 24:16

^bPs 71:20; 2 Tim 3:11f

^cPs 34:4, 6, 17

Psalm 34:20

^aJohn 19:33, 36

Psalm 34:21

¹Or *held guilty*

^aPs 94:23; 140:11; Prov 24:16

Psalm 34:22

¹V 21, note 1

^a1 Kin 1:29; Ps 71:23

^bPs 37:40

Targum

Psa. 34:1 Of David, when he disguised his intelligence before Abimelech, who dismissed him, and he left. ² I will bless the LORD at all times, his praise is always in my mouth. ³ My soul makes her boast in the word of the LORD; the humble will hear and rejoice. ⁴ Ascribe greatness in the presence of the LORD with me, and we will exalt his name together. ⁵ I sought instruction from the presence of the LORD and he answered me; and from all my fears he delivered me. ⁶ They looked toward him and received light; and their faces were not dismayed. ⁷ This poor one prayed; in the presence of the LORD it was heard, and he redeemed him from all his troubles. ⁸ The angel of the LORD encamps around those who fear him, and he saved them. ⁹ Recognize and see that the LORD is good; happy the man who has placed his trust in his word. ¹⁰ Have fear in the presence of the LORD, O you his holy ones; for there is nothing lacking to those who fear him. ¹¹ The sons of the lion became poor and were hungry; but those who seek the instruction of the LORD lack no good thing. ¹² Come, children, receive [teaching] from me; I will teach you the fear of the LORD. ¹³ Who is the man who seeks life, loves days in order to see good? ¹⁴ Guard your tongue from evil, and your lips from speaking deceit. ¹⁵ Turn from evil and do good; seek peace and pursue after it. ¹⁶ The eyes of the LORD are toward the righteous; and his ears, to receive their prayer. ¹⁷ The face of the LORD is wrathful against evildoers, to expunge their memory from the earth. ¹⁸ The righteous pray, and it is heard in the presence of the LORD; and from all their trouble he has delivered them. ¹⁹ The LORD is near to the brokenhearted; and the lowly in spirit he will redeem. ²⁰ Many evils encounter the righteous man; and from all of them the LORD delivers him. ²¹ He protects all his limbs; not one of them is broken. ²² The death of the wicked is bad, and those who hate the righteous man will be condemned. ²³ The LORD redeems the soul of his servants; and none who hope in his word are condemned. --

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction and Superscript

This Psalm is based on events in David's life which are described in the Midrash Shocher Tov. David asked the LORD what the value of madness was? The LORD replied that someday in David's life, he will need to become mad. David had escaped Saul's wrath by fleeing to the land of the Philistines with nothing but the sword of Goliath. Goliath's brothers were the bodyguards of Achish, King of the Philistine city of Gath. The brothers recognized David and asked the King for permission to avenge Goliath by killing David. After some hesitation, the King agreed. David prayed to the LORD upon hearing this, asking him to give him madness, which he once criticized. David was given madness. He wrote that the King and Queen owed him money on the city gates. The daughters of the King went mad. They shouted and raved insanely inside the palace, and David ranted outside. The King drove David away to rid himself of David and his madness. Afterward, David composed this Psalm in gratitude for the madness. In the culture of David's day a person who was insane (mad) was not killed. It was believed that the person had an evil spirit in them. To kill the person could bring the evil spirit into the killer.

Verse 1

No matter what happened to David, He always praised the LORD.

I shall henceforth praise the LORD at all times; I will praise His mighty acts, which will continually remain in my mouth.

Verse 2

My soul glorifies in the LORD; let the humble hear it and be glad.

Verse 3

David called upon the unfortunate to rally with him as they together declared the greatness of the LORD.

The humble and I declare that greatness of the LORD, and together we exalt his Holy Name.

Verse 4

דָּרַשׁ אֱלֹהִים (darash'tee) means "to seek with care." This word tells us that David sought instruction and inspiration from the LORD.

I sought the LORD, and He answered me, and delivered me from all my fears.

Verse 5

If you have the LORD in the center of your life you will discover that the LORD is a primary source of blessings and strength.

All people who looked unto the LORD received His power (His light), and their faces always shined the LORD's presence.

Verse 6 & 7

The poorest men who have sought out the LORD's help received it. That is a sign that the angel of the LORD encamps everywhere.

The poorest people cried out to the LORD, and He heard and has saved them from all troubles.

Thus, the angel of the LORD surrounds those who revere the LORD, and He has always delivered them.

Verse 8

This verse means that you should try to serve the LORD even if you have not decided to serve and follow the LORD. Then determine by your experience that the LORD is good.

Test the LORD for yourselves, and you shall see how good He is; how blessed are the people who trust in Him.

Verse 9

If a person feels that they belong to the LORD, they must demonstrate this desire and emotion. One must keep the LORD always in front of them (always living by His commandments).

O revere the LORD, you who are sanctified to Him, for there is no want to them that revere the LORD.

Verse 10

A person who does not place their lives into the hands of the LORD is like young lions who make physical desire their law and put their trust in their strength.

Young lions are poor and suffer hunger, but they who seek the LORD will never want for any good thing.

Verse 11

The psalmist offers words of advice. The following verses are addressed to young people. Materialism is not everything.

Come, O sons, hear me; I will teach you to revere the LORD.

Verse 12

Who is the person who desires life; who loves days that he may see good?

Verse 13

Keep your tongue from evil and your lips from deceitful language.

Verse 14

It is not always prudent to confront evil and fight against it. Sometimes it is better to avoid contact with it from the outset. Actively pursue good deeds fighting off the negative influences in the world. Sometimes the peaceful way is not the easy way.

Stay away from evil and always do good without hesitation; seek peace and pursue it.

Verses 15 & 16

These are promises from the LORD for those who follow Him and for evildoers.

The eyes of the LORD are looking at the righteous while His ear is open to their cry.

The countenance of the LORD is against people who commit evil and will cut off the memory of them from the earth.

Verses 17 & 18

The LORD does not limit his attention to only the righteous. He also responds to the cries of the humblest and downtrodden people.

Even the righteous cry, and the LORD hears them and delivers them out of all troubles.

The LORD is near the brokenhearted, and He saves such who are crushed in spirit.

Verses 19 & 20

The righteous people of the world who have been promised "life" and "good things" do not mean that they will never suffer. On the contrary, righteous people can expect significant troubles and calamities. These troubles are seen as a test of the righteous.

The righteous do suffer in life, but the LORD delivers them from it.

Verses 21 & 22

Disasters will eventually strike people who persist in their evil ways.

Evil will kill the lawless in the end, and they that hate the righteous shall be destroyed.

The LORD redeems the soul of His servants, and none of them who take refuge in Him shall be desolate.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

By David, when he became mad (at his request from the LORD) so that he would be driven away by Abimelech the King of Gath.

I shall henceforth praise the LORD at all times; I will praise His mighty acts, which will continually remain in my mouth.

My soul glorifies in the LORD; let the humble hear it and be glad.

The humble and I declare that greatness of the LORD, and together we exalt his Holy Name.

I sought the LORD, and He answered me, and delivered me from all my fears.

All people who looked unto the LORD received His power (His light), and their faces always shined the LORD's presence.

The poorest people cried out to the LORD, and He heard and has saved them from all troubles.

Thus, the angel of the LORD surrounds those who revere the LORD, and He has always delivered them.

Test the LORD for yourselves, and you shall see how good He is; how blessed are the people who trust in Him.

O revere the LORD, you who are sanctified to Him, for there is no want to them that revere the LORD.

Young lions are poor and suffer hunger, but they who seek the LORD will never want for any good thing.

Come, O sons, hear me; I will teach you to revere the LORD.

Who is the person who desires life; who loves days that he may see good?

Keep your tongue from evil and your lips from deceitful language.

Stay away from evil and always do good without hesitation; seek peace and pursue it.

The eyes of the LORD are looking at the righteous while His ear is open to their cry.

The countenance of the LORD is against people who commit evil and will cut off the memory of them from the earth.

Even the righteous cry, and the LORD hears them and delivers them out of all troubles.

The LORD is near the brokenhearted, and He saves such who are crushed in spirit.

The righteous do suffer in life, but the LORD delivers them from it.

Evil will kill the lawless in the end, and they that hate the righteous shall be destroyed.

The LORD redeems the soul of His servants, and none of them who take refuge in Him shall be desolate.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

